

WO₃ thin films grown on Si substrates: potential high *T_c* ferromagnetic semiconductors

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Received: 17 September 2024 / Accepted: 29 October 2024
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Abstract

Well-defined ferromagnetism (FM) with a very high *T_c* of about 800 K was found in laser-ablated WO₃ films grown on Si wafer substrates. It seems that the observed magnetism is surface related, and oxygen vacancies might play an important role in inducing FM into these oxide semiconductors. The very high *T_c* FM is observed for the first time in nanosized-WO₃, indicating a great potential for spintronic applications.

Keywords Magnetic semiconductors · Room temperature ferromagnetism · Oxide thin films · Defects · Oxygen vacancies

1 Introduction

Since 2000, magnetic semiconductors have been attracting the attention of material researchers due to their potential for spintronic devices [1]. Once semiconductors are manipulated to become ferromagnetic at room temperature, they can be used effectively for sustainable technologies since in that case, both charge and spin could be exploited in the same device. The advantages of spintronic devices are (i) they can lower power consumptions due to reduced heat dissipation; (ii) make data processing and switching faster. This method of spin manipulation for data storage uses much less energy because a spin current causes less resistance so it prevents overheating, and as a result, the information does not disappear when power is lost. In general, spintronics have several advantages over conventional electronics, which rely only on the charge of electrons. Over last years, many research groups have put a lot of efforts to clarify the nature of ferromagnetism (FM) in ultrathin layers of magnetic transition-metal (TM) oxides and in thin films of undoped oxide semiconductors that are usually non-magnetic in bulks (e.g., TiO₂, SnO₂), with prospects of

applications in spintronics, by well profiting their extraordinary properties due to low dimensionality and formations of surface related vacancies and defects [2]. Our objective is to explore magnetism in ultra-thin films of TM oxides depending on dimensionality and concentrations of oxygen vacancies and other defects. Room temperature FM was observed in undoped HfO₂, TiO₂, ZnO, In₂O₃, and SnO₂ thin films [3–8]. In many cases, it seems that oxygen vacancies and defects at the surface and sub-layers just below the surface of thin films are the main reason for the observed FM [2]. The objective is if once we can understand such a mechanism, then it is possible to manipulate the concentration of those vacancies and defects, in order to make materials potential for applications. Since pure oxides such as HfO₂, TiO₂, SnO₂, ZnO have been investigated a lot [3–10], we look for some new pristine oxides whose mechanism of FM has not been well understood so far. WO₃ is known for its great potential due to its optical and conductive properties, however, its magnetic properties have not been widely investigated [11]. WO₃ had been reported as a wide band-gap semiconductor with a great *n*-doping performance with excellent conductivities and high electron Hall mobility [12]. Optical parameters of WO₃ films such as transmission and reflections could be well manipulated by varying thermal treatments, then become suitable for devices [13]. WO₃ is one of the highly demanding functional metal oxides which finds immense interest in condensed matter physics and electrochemical devices [14–16]. Therefore, it is important to understand the magnetic behavior of WO₃

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in low-dimensional configurations for future applications in multifunctional storage devices.

In this study, we will report on our findings of WO₃ laser-ablated thin films with different thicknesses deposited on low-cost Si wafers. Since in many previous works on pristine oxide films, it shows that magnetic properties of oxide films are thickness dependent, raising from the fact that low dimensionality, therefore having confinement effects, would be the origin of room temperature ferromagnetism (FM) [2–4, 8, 17], we will study this issue as well.

2 Experiment

WO₃ powders have been synthesized by using a thermal treatment method by calcination of tungstic acid H₂WO₄ (99%, Sigma-Aldrich) at 500°C for 5 h. The powders are pressed into the pellet and then sintered at 1200°C for 1 h to form a ceramic target for film fabrications. Films of WO₃ were deposited by a pulsed-laser deposition (PLD) system from the ceramic target on Si wafer substrates with an energy density of 2 J cm⁻², and a repetition rate of 10 Hz. A Coherent COMPEX ultraviolet 248 nm KrF excimer laser was used for film elaborations. The distance between the target and the substrate is set at 55 mm. Heating rate is 50 °C/min and cooling rate is 25 °C/min. The oxygen pressure was kept as 0.01 mbar with the Ar: O₂ flow ratio was 50:50, and the substrate temperature was kept as 600°C. The thickness of WO₃ films varies from 40 to 320 nm. A typical deposition time for film of 80 nm thick was about 4 min. For the WO₃ powders, target and films, structural studies were done by X-ray diffractions (XRD) at room temperature. Morphology and chemical analysis were studied using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM JEOL JSM 7200 F, JEOL Ltd., Tokyo, Japan) and energy-dispersive spectroscopy (EDS Bruker XFlash 6-100, Bruker, Billerica, MA, USA), respectively. SEM pictures were taken at a 5 kV accelerating voltage. Additionally, high resolution X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were performed for the WO₃ films at room temperature. Magnetic moment (*M*) versus magnetic field (*H*) from 0 to 0.5 T and versus temperature (*T*) from 50 K up to 900 K was measured by using a VSM magnetometer. The magnetic field was applied parallel and perpendicular to the film plane. The thickness of the typical film was measured by using the NIR-UV spectroscopic ellipsometer J. A. Woollam V-VASE. If the film is on an opaque substrate, such as a wafer, optical reflectivity measurements can be used to measure its thickness. If the film is on a transparent substrate, or if the film itself is subjected to analysis, transmission measurements can be used to measure its thickness. The measurements were carried out for the very thin films below 100 nm to be precise, in the range

of light wavelengths from 400 to 1000 nm, and the Cauchy method was used to obtain the film thicknesses whose margin error is about 1% only. By knowing the refractive index of the film, one can calculate the thickness of the film using the formula: thickness = wavelength / (2 * refractive index * cos(θ)), where the wavelength is the wavelength of the light used, and θ is the angle of incidence of the light beam [18]. Then for thicker films, the approximate thicknesses were calculated from the number of pulses during the deposition since the thickness of the deposited thin film is proportional to the number of pulses.

3 Results and discussions

WO₃ films with different thicknesses deposited on Si substrates are single phase orthorhombic WO₃, and (001) oriented [19, 20]. One can see that due to the constraints from the substrates, in very thin films, such as 40 nm-thick-one, the peak of (001) is broader and intensity is more modest than that of the thicker ones, when the effects from the substrates are much less obvious (Fig. 1). The result is more than what we could expect, since Si is amorphous and much less expensive in comparison to other types of substrates. The morphology of the thinnest WO₃ film was shown in Fig. 2 (a), and its corresponding mapping EDS images show the W distribution (Fig. 2 (b)), and the O distribution (Fig. 2 (c)). The SEM image in Fig. 2 (a) shows the homogeneity of the 40 nm-thick-WO₃ film. Additionally, the EDS mapping reveals uniform distributions of W and O elements (seen from Fig. 2 (b) and (c)).

Magnetization versus magnetic field curves taken 300 K are shown in Fig. 3. One can see that all films are ferromagnetic at room temperature, however, the saturated magnetization for the thinnest film has the greatest magnitude. It is very similar to what was obtained in TiO₂ and SnO₂ systems, when it was found that the FM in those oxide has a 2D nature [2–4, 8, 17]. It suggests that the observed FM must be surface related, or in other words, if the FM is supposed due to defects and/or oxygen vacancies, then those must be located mostly at the surface and interface between film and substrate [2, 8]. This assumption is more enforced when we look at the raw data of magnetic moments (note that all films were deposited on the same size of substrate, so that data before normalizing can be compared directly one to another. The magnetic moments are 2.56×10^{-5} ; 8.67×10^{-6} ; 3.64×10^{-6} ; and 3.23×10^{-6} for films of thickness as of 40 nm; 80 nm, 160 nm, and 320 nm, respectively. As for films of 160 nm and 320 nm, the magnetic moments are almost the same, indicating that there is almost no contribution to spin moments from the layer further than 160 nm to substrate. There are some significant magnetic

Fig. 1 X-ray diffraction patterns of WO₃ films with different thicknesses grown on Si substrates and of a bare Si substrate

Fig. 2 SEM image of the 40 nm-thick WO₃ films (a) and EDS mapping images for (b) W and (c) O distributions

moments within a layer of 80 nm, but the greatest contribution lies within 40 nm taken from the surface. One would conclude that the FM observed in WO₃ films has a 2D nature. When the film is 320 nm-thick, it shows a weak ferromagnetic behaviour, and indeed its properties approach

that of the bulk, which is in fact diamagnetic at 300 K (see Fig. 4 for $M(H)$ for the WO₃ bulk sample). The oxide bulks are in general diamagnetic, as seen in HfO₂, In₂O₃, TiO₂, and SnO₂ [4]. It was explained that FM in undoped semiconducting oxides, since there is no 3d electrons, FM must

Fig. 3 Magnetization versus magnetic field taken at 300 K for WO_3 films with magnetic field applied parallel to the film's plane. The inset show the $M(H)$ curve measured at 300 K in the perpendicular configuration

originate from oxygen vacancies/defects that exist only in low-dimensional configurations [2], but not in bulks, when it is 3D. It was figured out that for example, in SnO_2 case, O and Sn vacancies, must be located in which surface or sub-surface nano-layer that may finally contribute to the total magnetic moment, how far from one another, not anywhere possible [2]. In other words, in normal 3D undoped TiO_2 , or SnO_2 , or WO_3 , there is no source of magnetic interactions that may induce magnetic moments [2, 4, 17]. The $M(H)$ at 300 K measured in the perpendicular configuration for the 40 nm - thick WO_3 film is shown in the inset of Fig. 3. In this configuration, when magnetic field applied normal to the film plane, the film shows a clear diamagnetic behaviour. It indicates that there is a strong anisotropy in this compound, or in other words, its FM is in-plane but not off-plane, confirming the nature of FM as of 2D, or in other words, surface related. Note back to the XRD figure to see

that only (001) peak is present. The magnitude of about 27 $\mu\text{m}/\text{cm}^3$ for the 40 nm - thick WO_3 film is largest value that has been reported so far. Films made by magnetron sputtering on porous Alumina substrates was reported as of 21 $\mu\text{m}/\text{cm}^3$ [21], but one should well note that those films were deposited on the substrates that were designed with pores to form defects intentionally. Our films were deposited on commercial Si wafer substrates with no specific pores or formation of defects. The similar FM at room temperature were found in HfO_2 [3]; TiO_2 [4], SnO_2 [8], ZnO [6]; In_2O_3 [4], but in the family of semiconducting oxides, WO_3 is quite new. WO_3 is also hard to form a stable phase that one can exploit. The magnitude of saturated magnetization (M_s) that we obtained for WO_3 is almost the same for TiO_2 (about 20 $\mu\text{m}/\text{cm}^3$), and 1 order larger than that of ZnO and In_2O_3 [4, 6]. We also note here that the results are reproducible, since samples made by different times of depositions with

Fig. 4 Magnetization versus magnetic field taken at 300 K for the WO₃ ceramic target

Table 1 Saturated magnetizations of WO₃ films and some other semi-conducting oxide thin films

Name	Magnetization (emu/cm ³)	Reference
WO ₃ 40 nm	27	This work
Nanoporous WO ₃ 136 nm	21.7	[21]
WO ₃ 230 nm	3.8	[25]
SnO ₂ 10 nm	23	[32]
SnO ₂ 80 nm	0.87	[33]
MgO 170 nm	6	[34]
ZnO 200 nm	0.89	[35]
CoO 110 nm	60	[36]
HfO ₂ 220 nm	0.1	[37]
TiO ₂ 25 nm	40	[38]

the same conditions have the same structural and magnetic characteristics. Saturated magnetizations for WO₃ and some other oxide films are listed in Table 1 so that one can have some clear comparisons.

People usually reported about room temperature only, and rarely mentioned about the exact Curie temperature (*T_c*),

due to limited availability of commercial magnetometers that can offer measurements up to 400 K in general. Theoretically, it was predicted a *T_c* above room temperature in Mn-doped ZnO [22], and Mn-doped ZrO₂ [23], and the FM and the predicted high *T_c* are attributed to double-exchange (DE) interactions in those compounds, due to a transition-metal doping. Experimentally, it is rare to observe high *T_c* in pristine semiconducting oxides. So far, there has been only a report on *T_c* of 880 K for the undoped-TiO₂ films [5]. We have achieved to observe a very high *T_c* as of 825 K for the WO₃ films. Magnetization versus temperature taken at 0.5 T is shown in Fig. 5. One can see that at about 825 K, when there is the intercept between the *M(T)* curve and *T*-axis, the WO₃ film goes through a phase transition from paramagnetic to ferromagnetic phase, and maintain ferromagnetic for the whole range of temperature below 825 K. The *dM/dT* vs. *T* plot was inserted into Fig. 5, in order to verify the precise *T_c*. The minimum of this curve seen at 800 K confirms that our WO₃ films has a transition to ferromagnetic phase

Fig. 5 Magnetization versus temperature taken at magnetic field of 0.5T (field is applied parallel to the film's plane). The inset show the dM/dT vs. T plot

at around 800 K, to be precise. This ensures the potential of this compound for spintronic applications.

As for other semiconducting oxides, it was supposed that their room temperature FM should originate from oxygen vacancies and/or defects [3]. In several cases, it has been pointed out that those defects should be located on and near the surface [2]. For WO_3 , there was some simulation work for the bulks, saying that ferromagnetic moment if any, should be attributed for W vacancies, while O vacancies are non-magnetic [24]. Experimentally, when one creates defects intentionally into WO_3 , FM could be obtained in films or nanowires [25, 26]. It was reported also that when the oxygen partial pressure during the film deposition increases, the magnetic moment decreases [21]. We performed XPS measurements for WO_3 films with various thicknesses. The ratios of W: O are 13.4: 86.6; 14.3: 85.7; 14.7: 85.3; and

15.4: 85.4 for films whose thicknesses are 40 nm; 80 nm; 160 nm, and 320 nm, respectively. One can see that the ratio of W: O is not changed much when thickness increases, indicating that the atoms' distribution is quite homogenous along the thickness. On the other hand, one should notice that since the theoretical ratio between W and O should be 1:3, there should also be some W deficiency in our films. The O 1s core-level spectra were deconvoluted to show the lattice oxygen (O_L) and oxygen vacancy (O_V) [27, 28]. The profiles of lattice oxygen and vacant oxygen in films with different thickness are shown in Fig. 6, and quantitative can be seen in Table 2. The 40 nm film, which has largest M_s , has most of oxygen vacancies, in comparing to films of other thicknesses. In the theoretical paper that calculated magnetic moments for each model of WO_3 bulks, it was assumed that only W vacancies would contribute ferromagnetic moment

Fig. 6 XPS spectra of (a–d) survey scan and (e–h) O1s of 40 nm-, 80 nm-, 160 nm-, and 320 nm-thick WO₃ films on Si substrates, respectively

Table 2 Ratio between lattice oxygen and vacant oxygen in WO₃ films with different thicknesses

Name	Oxygen vacancy (%)	Lattice oxygen (%)
WO ₃ 40 nm	51.29	48.71
WO ₃ 80 nm	44.66	55.34
WO ₃ 160 nm	42.92	57.08
WO ₃ 320 nm	39.92	60.08

to the total magnetic moment [29]. However, based on what we see in here, there must be the issue of 2D or surface, therefore, when modelling for films, the role of oxygen vacancies on the surface in inducing FM should be carefully considered. This is coherent with the drawn conclusion of Ref. 21. Discussions on the role of O vacancies related to FM found in oxides that were elucidated from O 1s spectra seen in XPS could be found in many other Refs. as well [30, 31]. Note that XPS measurements are mostly sensitive for the surface. Therefore, the relationship between W vacancies and O vacancies, and as consequences, how this ratio may influence magnetic moments of WO₃ films could not be determined precisely now. Some simulation work and other advanced measurements such as X-ray magnetic circular dichroism (XMCD) and variable energy positron annihilation spectroscopy (PAS) should be performed in the future to well clarify this matter.

4 Conclusions

Laser - ablated WO₃ films deposited on cost-effective Si wafer substrates are ferromagnetic with *T_c* of about 800 K. The largest magnetization found in 40 nm-thick film is 27 mT/cm³. The high *T_c* ferromagnetism observed in WO₃ films seem to be surface- related since there is a strong thickness

dependence. Some simulation work, as well as XMCD and PAS measurements are planned to do whenever it is possible in the future, to verify the role of defects and vacancies in high-*T_c* ferromagnetism in WO₃ thin films. The finding of room temperature FM in WO₃ film deposited on Si strongly suggests a new candidate for spintronic devices.

Acknowledgements The authors acknowledge the financial support from the GACR (Project No. 22–21547 S) and the MEYS (Project CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004572). The CzechNanoLab Project No. LM2018110, funded by MEYS CR, is gratefully acknowledged for the financial support of the measurements and sample fabrication at the Central European Institute of Technology (CEITEC). We sincerely thank M. Kiaba for his technical support concerning PLD, and P. Mikulik his help with film thickness determination. N. S. Pham would like to thank C. Bilot (CRISMAT, ENSICAEN, France) for her help with SEM-EDS measurements.

Author contributions Nguyen Sy Pham and Nguyen Hoa Hong contributed equally to this manuscript. Nguyen Hoa Hong is the PI of the project, managed fundings, has given concepts, interpreted data, wrote and edited the manuscript. Nguyen Sy Pham made samples, performed measurements, analyzed data, plotted graphs, and finally joined writing and editing of the final version.

Data availability All data were included in the paper. Further details are available upon request made to the authors.

Declarations

Ethical approval Nguyen Sy Pham, Nguyen Hoa Hong report financial support was provided by GARC and from MEYS. We declare our relationship with GACR, MEYS that includes only funding grants. We have no competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Competing interests Nguyen Sy Pham, Nguyen Hoa Hong report financial support was provided by GARC and from MEYS. We declare our relationship with GACR, MEYS that includes only funding grants. We have no competing financial interests or personal relationships that

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